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Being based on microdata at the level of individual Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER) allows the fine-grained analysis of the composition of academic personnel by gender and by seniority.

ETER includes data on academic personnel from **1086 universities in 28 countries** with a breakdown by gender.

Women represent 44.0% of the total academic population, but only 28.4% of senior positions.

We introduce a new indicator, called **Gender Equality Index**, calculated as the difference between the share of women in senior academic personnel and the share of women in total academic positions. The index is negative for 96.5% of European universities.

Universities specialized in **STEM disciplines** have the lowest level of Gender Equality Index.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Union is committed to improve the **fairness and inclusiveness of academic careers** with respect to gender issues and young researchers.

With respect to gender, the background situation is: women constitute a large share of the population of higher education students, both undergraduate and postgraduate, still a significant share of postdoc and junior positions in academic career, but their role in advanced academic roles decreases drastically.

The availability of microdata is an important contribution to the debate. It will allow a better understanding of the situation, by showing in great detail differences across individual universities. Which universities do exhibit a balanced gender structure of academic personnel? Where are they located? Are they large or small, generalist or specialist? Do we see disciplinary differences?

2. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

This ETER Brief is a first, preliminary effort to address this issue. In the following analysis we only consider universities, that is, Higher Education Institutions offering the highest degree, or the PhD (Institutional level=1 in the ETER terminology, offering ISCED 8 degrees). We leave for future analysis the coverage of non-university institutions, such as college, University of Applied Sciences (UAS), Fachhochschule or similar institutions, not offering the PhD (Institutional level=2 in ETER).

Data on gender of academic personnel is available only for a subset of countries in the latest available year (2020). While ETER includes **data from 39 countries**, data on gender is available for 28 countries in 2020. These countries represent the large majority of the higher education landscape in Europe. They are: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Cyprus, Germany, Spain, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Sweden, Slovakia, Turkey

United Kingdom. Overall, we have individual data on **1086 universities** with respect to the gender of academic personnel (total).

3. FINDINGS

A useful indicator to address the issue of gender equity is the share of women in total academic personnel. In Figure 1 we examine the distribution of this indicator in the overall population of universities for which ETER includes data (n= 1086). Academic personnel is measured in Head count (HC), in order to compare the total number with the discrete distribution of the gender.¹

Figure 1. Share of women in total academic personnel (HC). Year 2020

Overall these universities employ **1,339,181 academic personnel**, of which 749,662 male and 589,519 female (44.02%). At aggregate level it may be said that the contribution of female academic personnel is very significant. Overall, **women represent not much less than half of academic personnel**.

The shape of the distribution is interesting:

- A small group of universities shows a dominant share of women on academic personnel.
- Overall, **310 universities** (28.5% of the total) have a share of women equal or greater to 50%.

- There is a tail of universities (71, or 6.5% of the total) in which the share of women is equal or smaller than 30%. As many as **28 universities** (2.6%) have a share equal or smaller than 25%.

It is therefore interesting to try to understand better the underlying factors leading to the distribution of the share of women.

By exploiting the fine-grained structure of ETER data it is possible to explore the characteristics of top universities in terms of share of women in total academic personnel. The inspection of data of the top 20 shows a number of interesting findings:

- While many countries are visible, East European countries are represented more than proportionally.
- Specialist universities, or universities with a dedicated disciplinary specialization, are more represented than generalist ones.
- The size of universities, as measured by total size of academic personnel, is small to medium- no large university is represented in the top list.
- With a few exceptions the universities in the top list are relatively young, that is, born in XX century or even in the last 50 years.
- The most represented specializations are Humanities (Pedagogy, Education) and Medicine (Medical or Veterinary).

These findings confirm one of the key issues in the debate on gender in academic careers, that is the relatively weaker position of women in STEM disciplines and in specialist universities dedicated to science and technology. To get a better picture of this issue we investigated the bottom region of the distribution, or those universities in which the share of women is equal or smaller than **30% (71 universities) or 25% (28 universities)**. In both cases we find striking confirmation of the issue:

- In the bottom 71 list we find an overwhelming presence of technical, or engineering specialist universities in almost all countries.
- Some of the most visible and prestigious technical universities are found in the list of universities with the largest share of male personnel in countries such as Austria (Vienna University of Technology, Graz University of Technology), Switzerland (EPFL, ETH), Germany (Technical Universities of Berlin, Kaiserslautern, Karlsruhe, Darmstadt, Hamburg), Greece (National Technical University of Athens), Italy (Politechnic of Turin and Bari), Sweden (KTH Royal University of Te-

nology, Chalmers University of Technology), Netherlands (Delft University of Technology) or Spain (Technical University of Madrid, Polytechnic of Catalunya).

- also represented in the list are a few military schools and pontifical universities.

- interestingly, in the case of Italy all Institutes of Advanced Studies², that are typically strongly concentrated in STEM disciplines, are included in the bottom list (Gran Sasso Science Institute, Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies, IUSS of Pavia, Scuola Normale Superiore, IMT, SISSA).

This analysis does not exhaust the debate- it is rather an invitation to use available microdata to build up custom-made comparisons or benchmarking exercise, in order to understand better the **phenomena and design appropriate policies**.

As it is well known, the crucial gender issue is visible when moving from the aggregate number to the higher ladders of the academic career. ETER includes **data on senior academic personnel** with a breakdown by gender. The definition of senior academic personnel, taking into account country differences, is discussed below in greater detail.

With respect to the data on gender in total academic personnel we have a few missing countries (Hungary, Iceland, Malta, Serbia and United Kingdom). Overall, data on gender composition of senior academic personnel is available for 847 universities, still a large number.

Overall, these universities **employ 141,742 senior academics**, of which 101,532 men and 40,201 women (28.4% of the total). As it is immediately visible, there is a large gap between the average presence of women in total academic personnel (44.0%) and the presence in the higher I-academic career steps (28.4%).

We start by inspecting the overall distribution of the indicator (Figure 2). The shape of the curve is similar to the one found on the share of total academic personnel, but the curve is shifted downward significantly. On the one hand, there is a small group of universities for which the share of women is very large, up to 70% (with two very small outliers at 100%). But this tail of the distribution is small and does not influence the overall pattern.

Only 75 universities have a share of women in academic personnel equal or larger than the average share in total academic personnel (44.02%). This means that **91.1% of universities** have a share of senior academic personnel smaller than the European average intensity of women in total academic personnel.

Figure 2. Share of women in senior academic personnel (HC). Year 2020

As we have seen, **European universities employ 44% of their academic personnel from the female population**, but only approximately 28% when they appoint candidates for senior positions.

While the overall pattern is well known, less is known about the distribution of the phenomenon. Are universities similar in their pattern of recruitment of senior positions? Do we see differences? If yes, is there a (perhaps tentative) explanation?

In order to address this issue with micro-based evidence, we suggest a summary indicator. The indicator is built as the simple difference, at the level of individual universities, between the share of women in total academic personnel and the share of women in senior academic personnel. Being a difference between relative values, that is, shares that do not depend on the size of universities, it is scale-independent. Being calculated as the difference between two percentages it is easily interpreted.

Let us label it Index of Gender Equality (IGE) and define it with the following formula

$$IGE = ((\text{Number of women in senior academic personnel} / \text{Total number of senior academic personnel}) - (\text{Number of women in total academic personnel} / \text{Total number of academic personnel})) * 100$$

The larger the IGE number, the higher the equality of career opportunities for women. A negative index means that women do not have equal opportunities.

Each university in our dataset will have its own IGE. Each university may compare its own IGE with the European average (approximately -16%). Each university may also select a benchmark against which to be compared- a set characterized by size, nationality, legal status, age, subject mix or any other relevant variable that are similar to itself.

Being calculated regularly, year after year, universities might use it to monitor change (and hopefully progress).

Let us start with the analysis of the distribution of the indicator. The average IGE value (approximately minus 16%, or the difference between 44.0% and 28.4%) means that, on average, equality is not implemented. Figure 3 shows a remarkable pattern. Overall, **817 universities show a negative IGE**, that is, a share of women in senior academic positions smaller than the corresponding share in total academic personnel. They represent 96.5% of universities. Only 3.5%, or 30 universities, have an Index equal or larger than zero.

Two remarks are in order. First, an Index greater than zero does not mean that women are more than 50%, but simply that the share of women in senior academic position is larger than the share in the total academic personnel of the same university.

Second, please note that, since senior personnel is included in the calculation of total academic personnel, the Index is an underestimation of the phenomenon – the share of women in junior and intermediate academic personnel is larger than the average across the total academic personnel (which is reduced by the inclusion of a smaller than average share due to senior personnel one).

Therefore, if one would like to calculate transition probabilities (that is, the probability for women of moving upward to senior positions given the share of women at intermediate or junior positions), the picture would be even more problematic.

Figure 3. Distribution of universities by Index of Gender Equality

4. IMPLICATIONS

This Brief has shown the potential of microdata based on official statistics provided by National Statistical Authorities in addressing some hot policy issues in the European higher education landscape.

The use of microdata allows institutions to **self-reflect on their own strategy and positioning** with respect to peer institutions and against average values at national or European level. It allows governments and policy officials to evaluate their state of the art, implement policies, monitor progress, gain a deeper learning on the dynamics of the system.

The issues of career structures and gender equity are at the core of policy debate and deserve reflection and action.

ETER is committed to support the overall data infrastructure with reliable, updated and interpretable data, for the benefit of the entire European institutional landscape.

Notes

¹ In principle gender equity might refer to both male and female representation. In practice the most relevant issue is women under-representation. Data also include Unclassified gender as a separate entry. By inspection of the data it appears that the overall number of cases is negligible. While we recognize the qualitative importance of the classification we follow the ETER Handbook in using an indicator in which the denominator is the sum of male and female entries.

² Institutes of Advanced Studies are public institutions dedicated to post-graduate education (PhD) and/or undergraduate education with a highly selective model based on national admission competitions and stringent career constraints, based on the French model of École Normale. Although Humanities and Social Sciences are also included they mostly specialize in STEM disciplines.

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